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RP-HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF PARACETAMOL AND N-ACETYLCYSTEINE IN ITS BULK AND EFFERVESCENT TABLET DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

The present study describes a simple, accurate, precise and cost effective Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for simultaneous estimation of Paracetamol and N-Acetylcysteine in its bulk and effervescent tablet dosage formulation. The approach of research was to develop an effective RP-HPLC method since there were only few voltammetric methods which were voltammetric in nature. The developed method involved mobile phase containing Water: Acetonitrile in the proportion of 97:3 % V/V, at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min and oven temperature of 30° C. The analyte were resolved by using isocratic programme on HPLC system containing UV- visible detector with Shimadzu class VP Software and Inertsile C18 (250 mm × 4.6 mm i.d.) 5 µm column. The detection of N-Acetylcysteine and Paracetamol were carried out at 220 nm and the method was validated High linearity of the developed method was confirmed over concentration range of 40-80 µg/ml for Paracetamol and 40-80 µg/ml for N-Acetylcysteine with correlation coefficient of 0.999 and 0.999 respectively at selected wavelength. The percentage RSD for Precision and Accuracy of the method was found to be less than 2%. Peaks were obtained at Retention times of 14.6 & 5.3 min for Paracetamol & N-Acetylcysteine respectively. The major outcomes of the result were that the method showed good reproducibility and it is accurate, precise, specific and sensitive. It can be concluded that the proposed method can be successfully used for the estimation of Paracetamol and N-Acetylcysteine in combination dosage formulations.

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INTRODUCTION

Pharmaceutical analysis plays a very prominent role in quality assurance as well as quality control of bulk drugs and pharmaceuticals. Method development is the process of proving that an analytical method is acceptable for use to measure the quality, identity, quantity, safety, efficacy and purity of drug substance.¹ The main aim of the work is to design and develop a stable and highly effective analytical method for the determination of Paracetamol and N-Acetylcysteine from bulk and its effervescent tablets. The market survey revealed that Paracetamol and N-Acetylcysteine in combination are introduced in market as tablet and syrups dosage form. Literature survey also revealed that Paracetamol is official in IP, BP, USP and N-Acetylcysteine is official in USP, BP.^{2,3} As per literature survey only few analytical methods are reported for the Paracetamol and N-Acetylcysteine combination which is voltammetric by using the modified multi walled carbon nano tubes. There was no HPLC or Chromatographic method for above combination of drug reported earlier. In the present work an attempt has been made to develop an accurate, simple, precise and reliable method for estimation of the drug in their dosage form and to validate method as per ICH Guidelines.¹

Need for Research (Problem being tackled)

The market survey revealed that Paracetamol and N-Acetylcysteine in combination are introduced in market as tablet and syrups dosage form. As per literature survey only few analytical methods are reported for the Paracetamol and N-Acetylcysteine combination which is voltammetric by using the modified multi walled carbon nano tubes. There was no HPLC or Chromatographic method for above combination of drug reported earlier.

Objectives

The objectives of the present work were to develop simple, rapid, accurate, economical and sensitive RP-HPLC method for determination of Paracetamol and N-Acetylcysteine in combined effervescent dosage form and to validate developed RP-HPLC method as per ICH guideline.

Justification of research

Only voltammetric method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of Paracetamol and N-Acetylcysteine in the past. There was a need to develop an Reverse Phase-High Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) method which is more efficient than voltammetric method. Due to this reason, an attempt was made to develop an RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Paracetamol and N-Acetylcysteine in its bulk and effervescent tablet dosage form.

Analytical Method Development and Optimization²

Analytical method development consists of techniques, method, procedure and protocol. Based on the number of factors of drug we have to identify the method and perform the experiment for Analytical Method Development. Chromatography, specifically liquid chromatography (LC) in the form of HPLC is used enormously in pharmaceutical drug analysis. Methods are developed to support drug testing against specifications during manufacturing and finished product testing, as well as during long-term stability studies. Methods may also support safety and characterization studies or evaluations of drug performance. According to the ICH, the most common types of analytic procedures are identification of sample, quantitative tests of the active moiety in samples of API or drug product, quantitative tests for impurities content, limit tests for the control of impurities.

Phases of Analytical Method Development⁵

Development of analytical methods for Liquid Chromatography instrument systems is typically carried out in two phases.

Column screening (column scouting):

Column screening is the experimental work done to identify the analytical column (stationary phase) with the best selectivity in terms of all compounds in the sample which must be adequately resolved.

Method development:

This involves experimenting with additional instrument parameters believed to strongly affect compound separation.

TYPES OF HPLC^{6,7}

HPLC systems are classified into two categories: Based on Method

Normal Phase Chromatography

In normal phase chromatography, stationary phase is highly polar while mobile phase is non-polar solvent. Its specifications are mentioned in Table 1.

Table 1: Normal Phase Chromatography⁶

Attribute	Specifications
Stationary phase	It is a bonded siloxane with polar functional group like SiO ₂ , Al ₂ O ₃ , -NH ₂ , -CN, -NO ₂ , -Diol.
Mobile phase	Nonpolar solvents like heptane, hexane, cyclohexane, chloroform, ethyl ether, dioxane.
Application	Separation of nonionic, nonpolar to medium polar substances.
Sample elution Order	Least polar components are eluted first.

Reverse Phase Chromatography

In reverse phase chromatography, stationary phase is nonpolar and the mobile phase is relatively polar. Its specifications are mentioned in table 2.

Table 2: Reverse Phase Chromatography⁷

Attribute	Specifications
Stationary phase	It is bonded siloxane with nonpolar functional groups like n-octadecyl (C18) or n-octyl (C8), ethyl, phenyl, -(CH ₂) _n -diol,
Mobile phase	Polar solvents like methanol, acetonitrile, water or buffer (Sometimes with additives of THF or dioxane).
Application	Separation of nonionic and ion forming nonpolar to medium polar substances (carboxylic acids, hydrocarbons).
Sample elution Order	Most polar components are eluted first.

Based on Elution

Isocratic Elution:

It keeps the mobile phase constant during the course of separation.

Gradient Elution:

It is also called as “solvent programming.” It changes the composition of the mobile phase during the course of separation.

INSTRUMENTATION OF HPLC: ^{8,9,10,11}

The various components of HPLC are

1. Mobile Phase Reservoir
2. Pumps (Displacement Pump, Reciprocating Pump, Pneumatic Pump)
3. Sample Injectors
4. Pre columns
5. Liquid chromatographic column (Analytical Column)
6. Detectors

Strategy of Analytical Method Development

A strategy for developing chromatographic methods designed to determine impurities and degradation products in API or drug products. Selectivity is achieved by evaluating a stationary phase, mobile phase combinations, column, buffer, temperature, and gradient time chosen provide high peak capacities and allow operation at backpressures that can be achieved with standard instrumentation.

Fundamental Parameters of HPLC^{12,13,14,15}

Fig. 1 Fundamental Parameters of HPLC¹².

Where, $w_{1/2}$ = peak width at half height

w = band width of the peak (intersection point of the inflection tangents with the zero line)

A = peak front at 5% of peak height to peak maximum

B = peak maximum to peak end at 5% of retention times

t_0 = dead time of a column (retention time of unretarded substance)

t_{R1} , t_{R2} = retention time of components 1, 2.

t'_{R1} , t'_{R2} = net retention time of components 1, 2

Resolution (Rs)

It is a measure of quality of separation of adjacent bands in a chromatogram; obviously overlapping bands have small Rs values. It is calculated from the width and retention time of two adjacent peaks. Ideally RS should be greater than 2.

$$Rs = 2 (t_2 - t_1) / (w_1 + w_2)$$

Where,

t₁ and t₂ are the retention time of the first and second adjacent bands.

W₁ and W₂ are their baseline bandwidths.

Reliability of calculation is poor if Rs is < 2.0

Capacity factor (k)

It is the measure of the position of a sample peak in the chromatogram, being specific for a given compound, a parameter that specifies the extent of the retention of substances to be separated. *k* depends on the stationary phase, mobile phase, temperature and quality of column packing.

$$k_1 = (t_{r1} - t_0) / t_0 \quad k_2 = (t_{r2} - t_0) / t_0$$

Where,

t₀ = Dead time of column.

t_{r1}, t_{r2} = Retention times of 1st and 2nd eluting components.

Selectivity factor (α)

The selectivity of the chromatographic system is measure of the difference in retention time between two given peak. The selectivity factor α of a column for the two species A and B is defined as;

$$\alpha = K_B / K_A$$

Where,

K_B = distribution constant for more strongly retained species B.

K_A = distribution constant for less strongly or more rapidly eluted species A.

α is always greater than unity.

Number of theoretical plates (N)

The column efficiency can be expressed as the plate number (N) and HETP (Height equivalent to theoretical plate)

$$N = 16 [t_R^2 / W^2]$$

Where,

N = number of theoretical plates

w = width at the base of the peak,

N is proportional to the retention time of the compound and inversely proportional to the width of the peak.

Height equivalent to theoretical plates (HETP)

$$HETP = H = L / N$$

Where,

H = Height equivalent to theoretical plates (HETP)

L = Length of column (mm)

N = Number of theoretical plates.

Tailing factor (T)

The tailing factor (T) a measure of peak symmetry is unity for perfectly symmetrical peaks and its value increases as tailing becomes more pronounced.

$$T = W_{0.05} / f$$

Where,

f = Distance between maxima of two peaks

W_{0.05} = width of peak at 5 % height.

Ideally the T value should be < 2

Validation of analytical method¹³

Validation is defined as "documented evidence which gives a high degree of assurance that a process, system, facility will consistently produce a product or result meeting its predetermined specifications and quality attributes." They are mentioned in Table 3.

Table 3: Parameters for method validation¹³

As per ICH	As per USP
1) Accuracy	1) Accuracy
2) Precision, Repeatability and Intermediate Precision	2) Precision
3) Specificity	3) Specificity
4) Detection Limit	4) LOD
5) Quantitation Limit	5) LOQ
6) Linearity	6) Linearity and range
7) Range	7) Ruggedness
8) Robustness	8) Robustness

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Chemicals and Materials:

Paracetamol and N- Acetylcysteine were obtained as a gift sample from Sci Tech Specialities Pvt. Ltd. The formulation Paracetamol containing Paracetamol and N-Acetylcysteine was also obtained from Sci Tech Specialities Pvt. Ltd. HPLC grade water, methanol were obtained from Merck and potassium dihydrogen ortho phosphate was obtained from Fisher.

Instrumentation:

Quantitative HPLC was performed on waters liquid chromatograph with a UV detector equipped with automatic injector with injection volume 20 µl and 515 pump. A symmetry C₁₈ column (4.6 × 100 mm, 5 µm, Make: Hypersil) was used.

Ultra Violet spectrophotometric analysis:

The wavelength maxima was selected by using Shimadzu UV Spectrophotometer (UV-1700). 50 ppm stock solution of N-Acetylcysteine and Paracetamol were prepared in 0.1N NaOH separately. Wave length maxima were found to be 235 nm and 257 nm for N-Acetylcysteine and Paracetamol respectively. The solutions were scanned in the range of 200-400 nm, UV spectra of the two drugs was overlaid and a wavelength of 220 nm was selected for simultaneous estimation of the two drugs.

Method Development and Optimization:

To optimize the chromatographic conditions, the effect of mobile phase, pH and flow rate were studied. Various solvent systems were tried for the development of a suitable HPLC method for the simultaneous determination of N-Acetylcysteine and Paracetamol in its bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms. Mobile Phase tried for this purpose was Water : ACN (97 : 3) and pH adjusted to 3 with the help of O - Phosphoric Acid. The condition that gave best resolution and symmetry was selected. HPLC conditions are given in Table 4.

Table-4 Optimized Chromatographic Conditions¹³

Parameter	Specification
Column	C18, ODS Hypersil
Flow Rate	1.0 ml/min
Wavelength	220 nm
Injection Volume	20 µl
Oven Temperature	30 ⁰ C
Diluent	1) 0.1 N NaOH 2) Mobile Phase
Mobile Phase	Water : ACN (97:3)
pH	pH 3 with O-Phosphoric Acid
Run Time	20 min

Preparation of mobile phase:

30 ml of water was mixed with 970 ml of acetonitrile. The solution was degassed in an ultrasonic water bath for 5 minutes and filtered through 0.45µ filter under vacuum.

Preparation of buffer (pH 3):

7 gms of potassium dihydrogen phosphate was weighed and transferred into a 1000 ml beaker, dissolved and diluted to 1000 ml with HPLC water. The pH of the solution was then adjusted to 3 with orthophosphoric acid.

Preparation of standard solution:

32.5mg of Paracetamol was weighed and transferred to a 50 ml vol. flask, sufficient amount of 0.1 M NaOH was added to dissolve it & sonicated for 3 Min. The volume was made up with 0.1M NaOH and sonicated the solution for 5 Min.(STD1)

30mg of N-Acetylcysteine was weighed and transferred to a 50ml volumetric flask, sufficient amount of 0.1M NaOH was added to dissolve it and the solution was sonicated for 3 Min. The volume was made up with 0.1M NaOH and then sonicated it for 5 Min. (STD2)

Preparation of Mixed STD:

Dilute 5 ml STD 1 & 2.5 ml STD 2 to 50 ml with Mobile Phase. Sonicated for 5min. Inject Mixed Std to HPLC system.

Preparation of sample solution:

Seven tablets were weighed and crushed finely. Sample equivalent to 65 mg of Paracetamol and 120 mg of N-Acetylcysteine was weighed in a 100 ml volumetric flask, 50ml of 0.1 M NaOH was added to dissolve the sample completely. (The diluent was added slowly as sample get crepe). It was sonicated for 5 min. The sample volume was made up with 0.1 M NaOH. It was sonicated for 10 min. The sample was filtered with whatman no.42 & the filtrate was collected discarding first few ml of filtrate. 5ml of filtrate was diluted to 100 ml with Mobile Phase. It was sonicated for 2 Min. This sample for injection of HPLC.

Validation:

The method was validated for parameters such as linearity, precision, accuracy and selectivity.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Specificity:

The specificity checks included three test namely, identification test, interference test and peak purity of drug. Retention time of N-Acetylcysteine and Paracetamol was found to be 5.308 and 14.558 min respectively. No interference of the diluent, impurity, precursor and filter at the RT of N-Acetylcysteine and Paracetamol substance was found.

Precision:

Repeatability (Intraday precision) of N-Acetylcysteine and Paracetamol was determined by taking six replicates of 100% working level. The retention time and area of six determinations were measured and RSD was calculated. This indicates whether a method is giving consistent results for a single batch. Results are summarized in table no. 5.

Table 5: Calculation for precision.

Sr. No.	N-Acetylcysteine		Paracetamol	
	Retention Time (Rt)	Area	Retention Time (Rt)	Area
1	5.050	308041	13.942	1508797
2	5.042	308215	14.017	1508530
3	5.075	308163	14.292	1509241
4	5.108	308085	14.218	1508682
5	5.062	307991	14.078	1508719
6	5.038	308103	14.031	1508654
Mean		308099.6667		1508770.5
S. D.		80.98065613		246.56419
%RSD		0.026283916		.01634206

Linearity and range:

The linearity was determined by a series of five injections whose concentration level i.e.40, 50, 60, 70, 80 Correlation coefficient (r2), y-intercept was calculated and calibration curve plotted with the response (area) on y-axis and the concentration (amount) on the x-axis. Representative chromatograms and calibration curve for linearity and range are shown in figure 2 and 3 and table 6 and 7.

Fig. 2 Linearity graph of N-Acetylcysteine.

Table 6 – Linearity of N-Acetylcysteine.

Sr. No.	Level/Conc (PPM)	N-Acetylcysteine	
		Retention Time (Rt)	Area
1	40	5.100	203197
2	50	5.100	249682
3	60	5.083	300215
4	70	5.092	355526
5	80	5.075	396217
Correlation Coefficient			0.999093
Slope (m)			4918.84
Intercept (y)			-1.0750792

Fig 3: Linearity graph of Paracetamol.

Table 7: Linearity of Paracetamol.

Sr. No.	Level / Conc (PPM)	Paracetamol	
		Retention Time(Rt)	Area
1	40	14.625	739411
2	50	14.525	1328796
3	60	14.408	1895465
4	70	14.317	2471378
5	80	14.117	3036713
Correlation Coefficient			0.9999756

Correlation coefficient N-Acetylcysteine and Paracetamol was found to be 0.999 and 0.999 respectively. Above calibration curve proves that the response is linear throughout the range.

Accuracy:

Accuracy (% Recovery) studied were carried out by adding known amount of N-Acetylcystine and Paracetamol of concentration span 80%, 100% and 120% in triplicate. Results for % recovery are summarized in table no. 8 and 9

Table 8: Accuracy calculations of NAC.

Conc Level %	Retention Time (Rt)	Avg. Rt	Area	% Recovery	Avg % Recovery	SD	%RSD
80 %	5.108	5.110	237596	99.22	99.23	0.40525	0.40837
	5.108		238533	99.65			
	5.116		236701	99.84			
100 %	5.075	5.102	308664	99.66	99.74	0.08544	0.08566
	5.108		309223	99.83			
	5.124		308912	99.73			
120 %	5.133	5.131	361334	99.4	99.66	0.25106	0.25191
	5.133		363155	99.9			
	5.127		362389	99.69			

Table 9: Accuracy calculations of Paracetamol.

Conc Level %	Retention Time (Rt)	Avg. Rt	Area	% Recovery	Avg. % Recovery	SD	%RSD
80 %	14.650	14.604	1175901	101.29	101.28	0.06557	0.06474
	14.642		1176565	101.34			
	14.520		1176023	101.21			
100 %	14.292	14.409	1509244	100.52	100.61	0.08544	0.08492
	14.292		1512053	100.69			
	14.642		1510914	100.62			
120 %	14.633	14.647	1765506	100.18	100.11	0.05686	0.05679
	14.675		1764116	100.07			
	14.634		1764031	100.10			

% Recovery of N-Acetylcystine and Paracetamol was found to be 99.54% and 100.66%. % RSD of N-Acetylcystine and Paracetamol was found to be 0.2486 and 0.0688

System Suitability test:

The standard solution of N-Acetylcystine and Paracetamol was injected in six replicates and system suitability parameters were estimated and summarized in table no. 10

Table 10: System Suitability.

System Suitability	N-Acetylcystine		Paracetamol	
	Retention Time (Rt)	Area ($\mu\text{AU} \cdot \text{sec}$)	Retention Time (minutes)	Area ($\mu\text{AU} \cdot \text{sec}$)
Standard ($\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$)	5.050	281743	14.058	1578449
	5.075	281753	14.275	154813
	5.108	280806	14.483	1582610
	5.100	280454	14.317	1582255
	5.075	280710	14.233	1581963
	5.062	280593	14.362	1582889
Average (n=6)	5.078	281009.8333	14.288	11582163.167
Standard deviation	0.022	583.777155	0.141729139	2078.058942
%Relative Standard deviation	0.435	0.207742607	0.991946525	0.131342897
NTP	9420.13	9420.13	15345.212	
Symmetry factor	1.328	1.328	1.11	

Theoretical plates of Paracetamol and N-Acetylcystine were found to be 9420.13 and 15345.21 respectively. Symmetry factor of Paracetamol and N-Acetylcystine was found to be 1.328 and 1.11 respectively. Resolution was found to be 27.45. Capacity factor of Paracetamol and N-Acetylcystine was found to be 4.078 and 13.288 respectively.

Validation

Validation was performed as per the ICH guidelines for following parameters.

Specificity –

According to result of chromatograph of blank, placebo, and standard this method is specific for the N-Acetylcysteine and Paracetamol.

Accuracy –

Accuracy of the proposed method was ascertained from the recovery studies by standard addition method. %RSD observed is less than 2 %.

Precision –

Replicate estimation by the proposed method has yielded quite consistent result indicating repeatability of method. %RSD observed is less than 2 %.

Linearity and Range-

Paracetamol and N-Acetylcysteine were found to be linear in the range of 40-80µg/ml and 40 – 80 µg/ml with r2 equal to 0.999 and 0.999 respectively at selected wavelength.

System Suitability-

Method passes all criteria of the number of theoretical plates, resolution, symmetry, capacity factor.

CONCLUSION

Combination of Paracetamol and N-Acetylcysteine in effervescent tablet dosage form is available in market under the name Fluimucil Complex (effervescent tab), Dorbigot used for the symptomatic relief of Cough & fever. Multicomponent formulations are gaining precedence over single component formulations owing to the Synergism of effects, Reduction of cost of treatment, Increased patient compliance. Due to this rise in the multicomponent formulations, the challenges faced by the analytical chemist are also raised. Estimation of drugs from a multicomponent formulation requires a method capable of discriminating the two or more components. The present work involved the development of accurate, precise, simple and suitable RP-HPLC method for estimation of the drugs in multicomponent formulations. Present study was undertaken with an objective of developing suitable, sensitive and simple analytical method like RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of both drugs in their combined dosage form. Percent assay of N-Acetylcysteine and Paracetamol were reported as 99.54 % and 100.66 % respectively.

In RP-HPLC method, the analyte were resolved by using isocratic programme and mobile phase containing Water: ACN in the proportion of 97:03 %V/V, at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min, on HPLC system containing UV- visible detector with Shimadzu class VP Software and Inertsile C18 (250 mm X 4.6 mm i.d.) 5 µm column.

The detection of N-Acetylcysteine and Paracetamol were carried out at 220 nm. The method gave the good resolution and suitable retention time. The method was validated in terms of linearity, accuracy, precision, limit of detection, limit of quantitation, system suitability. The method showed good reproducibility and it is accurate, precise, specific and sensitive. No interference of additives, matrix etc. is encountered. Further studies on other pharmaceutical formulations would throw more light on these studies. The method was found to be sensitive, reliable, reproducible, rapid and economic. It can be concluded that the proposed method can be successfully used for the estimation of Paracetamol and N-Acetylcysteine in combination dosage formulations.

Future Scope of Research:

The method can be developed for estimation of the proposed drugs in bio-fluids. On the other hand, QbD approach can be applied to purposed analytical method to get the more optimized method.

Abbreviations:

°c -	Degree Centigrade
%	- Percentage
µg	– Microgram
µl	– Microlitre
ACN	– Acetonitrile
Avg	– Average
HPLC	– High Performance Liquid Chromatography
ICH	– International Conference on Harmonization
NAC	– N-Acetylcysteine

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Conflicts of Interest:

The authors report no conflict of interest

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